

Risk of patient-specific cardiac conduction abnormality (CCA) after transcatheter aortic valve replacement (TAVR) and dynamic insights from a beating heart model

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Introduction

Cardiac conduction abnormalities (CCA) is one of the major post-TAVR clinical complications as it may lead to permanent pacemaker (PPM) implantation (ranging from 2.3% to 25.9%). The membranous septum (MS) is located between the TAVR device landing zone and the conduction fibers. Analyzing mechanical factors such as contact force and logarithmic strain in the MS, can potentially assess the post-TAVR CCA risk on a patient-specific basis. This study employs a rigorous finite element-based *in silico* simulation of the TAVR deployment procedure in patient-specific aortic root models to assess the CCA risk. Additionally, the effect of pre-procedural parameters such as implantation depth, valve oversizing, and the orientation of calcium deposits as risk factors in developing post-TAVR CCA's were analyzed in a beating human heart model.

Methods

Two patients receiving balloon expandable TAVR devices were selected for this study. One patient required permanent pacemaker (PPM) implantation after TAVR, and one patient did not (control) and the patients received 29 mm Edwards Sapien XT and 23 mm Edwards Sapien TAVR devices, respectively. Patient-specific 3D models were generated from the CT images, MS regions were identified (Fig. 1a), and subsequently, TAVR deployments were simulated (Fig. 1b) following the methods described in our previous study [1].

Fig. 1: (a) Membranous septum (MS) and implantation depth measurement from CT and angiogram data, respectively (Used with permission from Cardiotech Publishing), (b) TAVR deployment, (c) Max. principal logarithmic strain contour, (d) Contact area. (e) Mean log strain (ϵ), and (f) contact force in the MS region vs time plot. (g) TAVR device placement (preload) inside the LHHM, and (h) Ventricular contraction of the LHHM after TAVR deployment. (i) Maximum principal logarithmic strain (ϵ) vs time in the AV node

Additionally, TAVR deployment was simulated in SIMULIA Living Heart Human Model (LHHM), a validated 3D dynamic model of an adult beating heart that includes physiologically realistic structural and electrophysiological properties (Simulia, Dassault Systèmes, Providence, RI) [2].

Results

Area weighted average log strain (Fig. 1e) (Mean log ϵ) and contact force (Fig. 1f) in the MS region, exerted by the TAVR device, were computed for both patients throughout the TAVR simulation. The peak of mean log strain (ϵ) and the contact force in the MS region of the PPM patient were observed to be higher than that of the control patient, indicating that these parameters can be analyzed to assess the risk of CCA after TAVR. Maximum principal logarithmic strain contour (Fig. 1c) and the contact area between the valve prosthesis and the MS (Fig. 1d), after the TAVR deployment simulations are also presented. The study is being extended to analyze the effect of additional factors on the development of post TAVR CCA in LHHM (Fig. 1g,h), such as implantation depth, valve oversizing, and calcium deposit size and orientation. The initial study has demonstrated a higher maximum log strain (ϵ) in the proximity to the atrioventricular node (Fig. 1i). Mean log strain (ϵ) in the MS region and the proximity to the conduction fibers are also computed to analyze the factors contributing to the development of post-TAVR CCA under dynamic beating heart conditions.

Conclusions

The study presents a computational framework to assess CCA risk associated with TAVR procedure on a patient-specific basis. It was currently extended to include beating heart effects on the factors associated with the development of post-TAVR CCA risk. It can potentially help clinicians to gain better insight into post-TAVR CCA risk and may offer preprocedural planning to minimize the risk.

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Reference

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